

Assessing sanitation, availability, and accessibility of western toilets in Jaipur for the elderly, people with disability, and pregnant women

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ABSTRACT

India has been a country with scarce availability of toilets in homes and even fewer at public levels. This glaring basic need has gotten a lot of attention and was made a national issue with the Swachh Bharat scheme introduced by PM Modi. For several years the government machinery has been trying to install toilets across the country. But have things improved as much for the disabled, senior citizens, and pregnant women, viz their defecation needs? Are these toilets at home accessible and usable for this set of people with special needs? This research paper is a statistical survey of two panchayats, Durjaniyavas and Machwa in Jaipur, to assess the physical problems faced by women, senior citizens, and disabled citizens while using the toilets within India and how this problem can be addressed. While doing this research study special focus has been given to the following factors: income levels, size of family, availability of water connections, and number of disabled people within the family. These factors may affect the decision of the families to install toilet facilities within their houses or use public facilities that are convenient to the disabled group of people. Our conducted survey suggests that in the panchayat of Durjaniyavas and Machwa on average the affected people i.e. physically disabled, with knee problems and pregnant women are 6%, 21%, and 4% respectively. The average number of old citizens living in these two panchayats is around 6%. Our study reveals that due to their health issues, it is uncomfortable for them to use an Indian toilet.

Keywords: *Health Issue, Durjaniywas, Machwa, Jaipur, Toilets, Open Defecation, Swachh Bharat Scheme*

1. INTRODUCTION

Toilets and safe drinking water are considered basic rights and important for the "full enjoyment of life and all human rights", as established by the UN General Assembly in 2010. According to the joint monitoring program, about 520 million people defecated openly as of 2017 (Jain et al., 2019) and in a study by Ambesh and Ambesh (2016), open defecation in India is estimated to be practiced by 600 million people per annum. The central rural sanitation program founded in 1986 ensured various subsidies for individual sanitary facilities throughout India. Studies in China and Uzbekistan have strengthened the conviction that there is a relationship between sanitation, water supply, and waterborne diseases (Jain et al., 2019). Women are one of the most vulnerable groups. Women need toilets not only for defecating but also for menstruation and issues related to pregnancy. During this period since they face danger from acts of sexual offense and other issues, they cannot openly defecate, they may reduce their meals leading to a negative impact on maintaining their health. The government of India is trying its very best to make toilets under the

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan while putting women at the forefront of this scheme (LSE International Development, 2023). To reduce the problem of open defecation the government should work with people to spread sanitation practices and bring about a countrywide behavioral change. For instance, the study, "Demographic, social and economic factors affecting the adoption of green toilets among rural households in India" by Ali and Khan, states that in the rural village of Dhaktode women face a problem due to not being free to openly defecate which is why they need proper sanitary laboratories (Ali et al., 2023).

Squatting, the natural posture for bodily waste elimination has been suggested to offer protective benefits against Colorectal Cancer. The research proposes that squatting aligns the colon, easing the passage of waste and reducing strain. This posture may aid in preventing chronic constipation and reducing the risk of Colorectal Cancer development (Sohrabi, 2012). Squatting also helps in preventing constipation, and appendicitis. Another benefit of Squatting is that Indian toilets are more hygienic. As there is no direct contact of the body with the Indian toilet seat, it is more hygienic compared to Western toilet seats, which reduces the risk of UTI (Urinary Tract Infection). Using the Indian Toilet is a kind of Exercise: The Indian Toilet position is kind of like a squat exercise. Sitting in such a position strengthens our leg muscles and bones. Indian toilets help in better digestion: Sitting in a squat position helps to digest the food properly. It even lays pressure on the bowel movement so that the waste goes out properly [Suri et al., 2022]. Even Though there are significant benefits to using Indian toilet seats, it is difficult for elderly, injured, disabled, and pregnant women to use Indian toilet seats.

The total number of toilets installed in India under the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) is 11cr since its launch, which is fairly substantial, and has helped a great deal in addressing the problem of open defecation. However, as per the study by Agarwal and Jain (Agarwal 2018), more than 20% of the population may not be able to use the Indian toilets installed under the SBM program. This population comprises people with disability, the elderly, and pregnant women. As per studies by Chakrabarti et al (2022), squatting may lead to higher chances of strokes and an accidental slip in the case of the elderly. Coffey et al. (2014) observed that 21% of the population in the sample did not use a toilet even when one was available. Addressing the issue of accessibility and squatting, studies from Ethiopia and Mali show that people are 3 times more likely to use modified toilets as squatting was an obvious problem faced by the elderly and people with disabilities. Agarwal (2018) and Jain et al. (2019), state that the physical prerequisites for squatting and standing up safely include two well-functioning ankles, knees, and hip joints, intact and healthy femur and tibia; the system of muscles, tendons, and ligaments to support them and a healthy heart, nervous system, and blood volume to maintain blood pressure with the change in position. This may be difficult to achieve for a person with a disability, the elderly, and even pregnant women in most cases. Western toilets are expensive to install as per Von Munch and Milosevic. Additionally, western toilets are highly maintained and require relatively more water consumption. In rural India water scarcity is prevalent and there are

multiple budget constraints, hence, installation of western toilets becomes challenging. This is corroborated by studies that show that 5% of the toilets are Western in rural India, unlike urban areas where it is as much as 40% [Milosevic, 2015]. This study aims to conduct a survey and identify the present number of disabled, elderly, and pregnant women. The survey has been conducted in the villages of Jaipur.

2. METHODOLOGY

- **Research Design** - The study is based on and survey of 165 households in Jaipur. See Appendix A for the survey form questions.
- **Sample** - 165 Households (HH) in panchayats of Durjaniwas and Machwa with a total population size of 2000 HH
- **Nature** - To do a random sample survey of 165 HH to figure out the percentage of the disabled/pregnant women /elderly in a 2000 HH population in two panchayats of rural Jaipur with limited access to toilets.
- **Technique** - Random sample, followed by both quantitative and qualitative analysis of the data set to understand the focus group as a percentage of the total
- **Size** - 165 of 2000+ HH
- **Scale used/tools used/instruments used** - Self-designed questionnaire
- **Data collection procedure** - Face-to-Face survey

Ethical Considerations

For this study, consent was taken from all participants before conducting the survey. Additionally, any bias regarding the representation of primary data or misleading information will be avoided. Research participant’s protection of privacy and confidentiality will be ensured.

Significance and Expected Outcomes

Understanding of the current hygiene and sanitation practices and highlighting the inaccessibility of western toilets for elderly, disabled, and pregnant women in rural India.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The survey has been conducted in two panchayats of Jaipur: Durjaniyvas and Machwa. Through the pain survey, health-related problems are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Affected Households

Affected HH	Durjaniyawas	Machwa	Average
Physically Disabled	2.08%	11.59%	6.06%
Knee Problems	17.71%	26.09%	21.21%
Pregnant Women	6.25%	0.00%	3.64%
No Problem	77.08%	60.87%	70.30%
Other	1.04%	4.35%	2.42%

According to Figure 1, the percentage of households as a percentage of the total who had at least one member as either a disabled person, a pregnant woman, or a person with a knee problem was almost 30% overall, but the percentage of the same was higher at Machwa compared to Durjaniyawas. It is best to emphasize the average of 21%, which is an important aspect that has come out in the survey, this is true for both Durjaniyawas and Machwa, it was also observed that the number of pregnant women was almost nil in Machwa, though the same was 7% in Durjaniyawas, this may be just a result of random results and hence we should take the average at 3%. The percentage of disabled was significantly higher at Machwa, which may be an overestimation due to the HH selected, so we should take the average of 6%. This should be a fair estimate considering the sample size is large, and the percentage of the elderly was observed to be similar at 7% at both the survey sites, it would be fair to assume a part of the elderly population may have difficulty in using Indian Toilets as highlighted earlier in several studies.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the affected households

Table 2: Scale of Pain Endurance

Scale of Problem	Durjaniyawas	Machwa	Average
1	84.38%	79.71%	82.42%
2	8.33%	8.70%	8.48%
3	4.17%	5.80%	4.85%
4	1.04%	2.90%	1.82%
5	2.08%	1.45%	1.82%

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the scale of problems

Building on the above the primary objective of the survey was to assess the degree of difficulty in using Indian toilets, here we found that 82% felt they did not have any significant problems in using Indian Toilets, even though we feel there may be a significant underestimation due to old habits and people not having tried the alternative in the past, we think that the survey numbers are quite large in itself, The % of people in the range of 2 to 5 it's almost 18%, which quite significant, almost 10% is actually between 3 and 5, this is a significant part of the population (refer figure 2).

Table 3: Income Level Representation

Income levels	Durjaniyawas	Machwa	Average
<60K	37.50%	56.52%	45.45%
60k-120K	43.75%	17.39%	32.73%
120K-240K	13.54%	11.59%	12.73%
>240K	5.5%	15.94%	9.70%

Figure 3: Graphical representation of income levels

In both Durjanियawas and Machwa, almost 80% of the people live with HH incomes of less than 10,000 per month, if this is added to the average HH size of 7 people, this means an average monetary value of 50 per day per person, this is very low-income levels, so the solution has to be at panchayat level. The population making more than 10,000 per month is less than 20%, though it seems to be higher at 26% at Machwa compared to Durjanियawas (from Figure: 3).

Table 4: Availability of Amenities

Basic Amenities	Durjanियawas	Machwa	Average
Water Connection in Home	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Western Toilet		20.29%	8.48%
Water Connection in toilet	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Figure 4: Graphical representation of availability of amenities

In both the panchayats the availability of water is very inspiring, the survey was done in Rajasthan, at close proximity to Jaipur, the closeness to a large urban area may be the reason for the same, so there may be a significant overestimation bias in this, but almost all toilets, 100% of the HH has water connectivity. The availability of western toilets in some HH at Machwa may be due to the higher income families at Machwa or proximity to an urban hamlet (refer to figure 4).

Table 5: Elderly population

	Durjaniyawas	Machwa	Average
Elderly percentage of the population	7.43%	4.99%	6.41%

Figure 5: Graphical representation of senior citizens in Durjaniyawas and Machwa

The percentage of elderly in both Durjaniyawas and Machwa is similar at 6%, we have seen the elderly are another set of people who may benefit from western toilets due to reduced risk of bathroom accidents and age-related comfort (refer to figure 5).

4. CONCLUSION

Keeping in mind our general hypotheses, we feel that the disabled, people having serious knee or back problems women who are pregnant, and the elderly in general, will greatly benefit if we can have community access to western toilet seats as a certain percentage of the overall toilets available keeping in mind the human and economic importance of reducing defecating in open. We feel an alternative of installing western toilets in at least 20% of the toilets under SBM will add to both, the convenience of the target group and will help in reducing the economic waste due to open defecation We do understand that Indian toilets are better biologically in certain ways and surely are more cost-effective, easy to maintain and finally water conserving but this can be mitigated by finding a solution which is equally efficient but also serves the greater purpose of humane solution to open defecation.

According to our study, we observed that there is a significant percentage of people who may have a variety of problems including pregnancy, periods, mental health disorders, physical impairments, and old age. In such cases using an Indian toilet becomes difficult since using such a form of toilet causes one to sit in the squatting position and a lot of pressure is applied on our forearms. Since many of these individuals are not able to support the pressure of getting up, going to a lavatory becomes quite the ordeal for this target group. Since not all villages may

receive equivalent amounts of water along with the expense of western toilets, the government must address this issue for the convenience of the target population.

5. LIMITATIONS

- The accuracy of the responses recorded can be a limitation as self-reported data may be impacted by bias and social desirability.
- Due to the sample size being limited to the location of Jodhpur, this might not provide a comprehensive view of the problem across the country.
- Since the study focuses on the elderly, citizens with disability, and pregnant women, it does not delve deeper into gender-specific issues that affect accessibility.
- The current study does not fully explore the implementation and effectiveness of government policies such as the Swachh Bharat scheme. Future studies can try to incorporate this aspect.

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Appendix

सर्वेक्षण फॉर्म

नाम: _____ पिता/ माता का नाम: _____

आयु: _____ मोबाइल नंबर: _____ लिंग: पुरुष महिला अन्य

पता: _____

गाँव: _____ ज़िला: _____

समस्या का प्रकार (कृपया निम्न में से एक चुनें):

- शारीरिक रूप से विकलांग गर्भवती महिला वृद्ध नागरिक घटने के रोग से पीड़ित
 कोई भी समस्या नहीं अन्य (कृपया विवरण दें): _____

आपकी समस्या कब से शुरू हुई?

आपकी समस्या की गंभीरता स्तर (कृपया निम्न में से एक चुनें):

- माध्यम अधिकांशतः गंभीर अत्यंत गंभीर

क्या इस समस्या के कारण इंडियन टॉयलेट के उपयोग में आपको परेशानी आती है?

वोटिंग स्केल 1 से 5 तक के माध्यम से चुनें, जहां 1 कम प्रभाव और 5 अधिक प्रभाव दर्शाता है:

1 - कम प्रभाव 2 - कुछ प्रभाव 3 - मध्यम प्रभाव 4 - अधिक प्रभाव 5 - बहुत अधिक प्रभाव

आपने इस समस्या के लिए किसी चिकित्सक/वैद्यकीय पेशेवर से परामर्श लिया है?

- हाँ नहीं यदि हाँ, तो कहाँ _____

क्या आपको सरकारी या अन्य संसाधन से इस समस्या में राहत के लिए कोई सहायता प्राप्त हुई है?

- हाँ नहीं यदि हाँ, तो _____

क्या आपके घर में पानी का कनेक्शन है?

- हाँ नहीं

क्या आपके घर में फिल्टर्ड पानी की सुविधा उपलब्ध है?

- हाँ नहीं

आपके घर में किस प्रकार का टॉयलेट है?

- इंडियन टॉयलेट वेस्टर्न टॉयलेट दोनों प्रकार के

क्या आपके टॉयलेट में पानी का कनेक्शन है?

- हाँ नहीं

आपके परिवार में कितने लोग हैं?

आपके परिवार की औसत आय क्या है?

- 5000 से कम 5000 - 10000 10000 - 20000 20000 से ऊपर